

The French Riviera of the East

Dr. M. Lavanya, M.A., B.Ed., M.Phil., Ph.D.
Assistant Professor, Department of History,
Kamaraj College, Thoothukudi – 628005.
lavanyaghukan@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

“The French Riviera of the East” is the advent of the French colonialization in India. Puducherry is the Tamil interpretation of “new town” and mainly arrived from “Poduke”. The consequential history of Pondicherry can be divided into three sections namely ancient history, medieval history and modern history. After the French colony was established this gave an altogether new social, political and economic history to this union. The Cholas were the first ones to rule the state during the medieval period. After the Cholas came the Pandyas who ruled the region starting from the thirteenth century till the fifteenth century. The modern history finally came to an end. There were constant conflicts between the English and the French and the reign of the region moved between them till 1816 after which the French gained authority of Pondicherry until it became the union territory in 1954. In exercise of the powers conferred by Article 239 of the Constitution of India and Section 46 of the Government of Union Territories Act 1963, the President of India has framed the Business of the Government of Puducherry (Allocation) Rules, 1963. Their presence played a very important role in giving shape to the modern history of Pondicherry and the flourishing commerce, trade, education and infrastructure in the region.

Key Words: French Riviera, French colonialization, Modern history, Puducherry, Cholas.

Introduction

Puducherry, formerly known as Pondicherry, gained its significance as “The French Riviera of the East” after the advent of the French colonialization in India. Puducherry is the Tamil interpretation of “new town” and mainly arrived from “Poduke” , the name of the marketplace as the “Port town” for Roman trading, way back in 1st century as mentioned in the ‘The Periplus of the Erythraean Sea’. The settlement was once an abode of many learned scholars as evidently versed in the Vedas, hence also known as Vedapuri. The consequential history of Pondicherry can be divided into three sections namely ancient history, medieval history and modern history. After the French colony was established which gave an altogether new social, political and economic history to this union territory.

History Of Puducherry

“Puducherry” is the French interpretation of the original name “Puducheri” meaning “new settlement”. Many pilgrims have shared the town’s hospitality on their way to the temple town of Rameshwaram, thus enriching its culture. The history of Puducherry dates back to the beginning of our era. Puducherry also had a flourishing maritime history. Excavations at Arikamedu, about 7 kms to the south of the town, show that Romans came here to trade in the 1st Century AD. The trade included dyed textiles, pottery and semi-precious stones. The findings are now displayed in the Puducherry Museum. Ancient Roman scripts mention one of the trade centres along the Indian coast as Poduca or Poduke, which refers, historians affirm, only to the present Puducherry.

Early Times

The history of Puducherry can broadly be classified in two periods- Pre Colonial period and Colonial Period. The "Bahur Plates", issued in the 8th century speak of a Sanskrit University which was here from an earlier period. Legend has it that the sage Agastya established his Ashram here and the place was known as Agastiswaram. An inscription found near the Vedhapuriswara Temple hints at the credibility of this legend.

History continues at the beginning of the fourth century A. D. when the Puducherry area is part of the Pallava Kingdom of Kanchipuram. During the next centuries Puducherry is

occupied by different dynasties of the south: in the tenth century A.D. The Cholas of Tanjavur took over, only to be replaced by the Pandya Kingdom in the thirteenth century. After a brief invasion by the Muslim rulers of the North, who established the Sultanate of Madurai, the Vijayanagar Empire took control of almost all the South of India and lasted till 1638, when the Sultan of Bijapur began to rule over Gingee.

The Pre Colonial period started with the reign of the Pallavas who continued to rule the empire from 325 A.D. – 900 A.D., then came the Chola dynasty for the time period from 900 A.D. – 1279 A.D., continued by Pandya Dynasty from 1279 A.D. -1370 A.D. During 14th Century, it was under the rule of the Naikship of Gingee denoting the Vijayanagar Empire from 1370 A.D. – 1614 A.D which was conquered by the Sultan of Bijapur and he continued for the phase from 1614 A.D. - 1638 A.D. It was during the period of the Sultan when the Portuguese and Danish merchants used the place as the trading center.

Ancient Times

Pondicherry was always a region which had developed commercially before any of the other major cities or towns of India. The region of Arikademu, which is situated at a distance of 7 km from Pondicherry, was said to be on good trading terms with the Romans ever since the 1st century. It was one of the best and growing trade centres in the country.

Roman manuscripts talk about 'Poduca' as an emerging centre for trade on the eastern coast of India and archaeologists believe that Poduca refers to Pondicherry. In the 4th century, Pondicherry was ruled by the Pallavas. Sanskrit University mentioned on the Bahur plates draw the academic background in the region during that time. Also, there are writings on the Vedhapuriswara Temple which indicate that Agastya, who was a very wise saint, set up an ashram in this region of Pondicherry.

Medieval Times

South India, which included the region of Pondicherry, was ruled by the Pallavas during the period of 4th to 10th century. The Pallavas faced a lot of conflicts with the Pandyas and Cholas who also succeeded them in ruling Pondicherry. The Cholas were the first ones to rule the state during the medieval period. After the

Cholas came the Pandyas who ruled the region starting from the thirteenth century till the fifteenth century.

During this time, the territory also witnessed Muslim rulers who spread their powers from North to South India and set up Madurai as their administrative centre. After the Muslims, came the Vijayanagar Empire which ruled entire South India. They ruled till the seventeenth century. Then the region was ruled by the Sultan of Bijapur. This marked the beginning of the modern history of Pondicherry. He ruled till 1638 AD.

Foreign Relationship

The Arab merchants, who had been sailing the coasts of India since times immemorable, the impact of European contact had far reaching consequences in terms of establishments and in the end the occupation of the entire Subcontinent. In 1497 the Portuguese discovered the route to India and began to expand their influence by occupying coastal areas and building harbour towns, which soon extended more than 12,000 miles of coast-line.

The Portuguese established a factory in Puducherry at the beginning of the sixteenth century, but were compelled to leave a century later by the ruler of Gingee, who found them unfriendly. After that the Danes shortly set up an establishment, and likewise the Dutch. The latter set up trading posts in Porto Novo and Cuddalore. The French, who had trading centres in the North, Mahe and Madras were invited to open a trading centre in Puducherry by the new ruler of Gingee to compete with the Dutch.

French Rule

Foreign countries started to influence the territory right from the start of the 16th century. It has been an important port and has been an active participant of the marine activities for a really long time. After it was realized what kind of importance is played by the east coast of India, everybody starting from the Portuguese, Dutch, Danes till the English began to establish colonies in this region. By the increasing foreign influence, the economic, as well as the commercial sector of the region, raised.

The French rule started in the 17th century after Bellanger who was a French officer established his residence in Danish Lodge which was a part of Pondicherry. In

1673, February 4th, Bellanger, a French officer, took up residence in the Danish Lodge in Puducherry and the French Period of Puducherry began. The rulers of Gingee invited the French to set up trading units in the region. In 1674 Francois Martin, the first Governor, started to build Puducherry and transformed it from a small fishing village into a flourishing port-town. His constant efforts enhanced the region and helped it grow into an emerging trading center. Pondicherry was occupied by the Dutch in 1693 and fortified the town considerably. But, after Holland and France came to an agreement, Pondicherry came under the influence of the French in 1699. In the 18th century the town was laid out on a grid pattern and grew considerably.

Able Governors like Lenoir (1726-1735) and Dumas (1735-1741) and an ambitious Governor Dupleix (1742-1754) expanded the Puducherry area and made it a large and rich town. But ambition clashed with the English interests in India and the local kingdoms and a period of skirmishes and political intrigues began. Under the command of Bussy, Dupleix's army successfully controlled the area between Hyderabad and Cape Comorin. But then Robert Clive arrived in India, a dare-devil officer who dashed the hopes of Dupleix to create a French Colonial India. After a defeat and failed peace talks, Dupleix was recalled to France.

In spite of a treaty between the English and French not to interfere in local politics, the intrigues continued. Subsequently France sent Lally Tollendal to regain the French losses and chase the English out of India. After an initial success they razed Fort St. David in Cuddalore to the ground, but strategic mistakes by Lally led to the loss of the Hyderabad region and the siege of Puducherry in 1760. In 1761 Puducherry was razed to the ground in revenge and lay in ruins for 4 years. The French had lost their hold in South India. There were a number of conflicts between the French and the English. The British occupied Pondicherry in 1760 after which the British army destroyed Pondicherry.

In 1765 the town is returned to France after a peace treaty with England in Europe. Governor Law de Lauriston set to rebuild the town on the old foundations and after five months 200 European and 2000 Tamil houses had been erected. During the next 50 years Puducherry changed hands between France and England with the regularity of their wars and peace treaties. The French gained supreme power over the region in 1816 but lasted till 1954 after Pondicherry became a union territory.

French Influence

The Influence of the Portuguese, Danes, Dutch and English. The Portuguese were the first ones to get settled in Pondicherry. They set up a factory in the sixteenth century which was shut down after a century. The rulers of Gingee, who had initially asked them to set up trade in the region, lost faith in them which led to the evacuation of the Portuguese from the region. The Portuguese were followed by the Danes and the Dutch who set up trading centres in Porto Novo and Cuddalore.

However, Portuguese, Danes and the Dutch were not able to prevail as long as the English and French in Pondicherry. The rulers of Gingee then invited the French to compete with the Dutch and set up their trade in the region. After the rulers of Gingee lost faith in the Portuguese, they invited the French to set up their colonies and begin their trade in Pondicherry. Portuguese were the first ones to set up trading centres in the place followed by the Danes and the Dutch who set up trading centres in Poto Novo and Cuddalore.

After 1816 the French regained permanent control of Puducherry, the town had lost much of its former glory. Churches, as well as forts, were established in Pondicherry and the architecture of the region grew. Successive Governors improved infrastructure, industry, law and education over the next 138 years

Conclusion

The modern history finally came to an end. There were constant conflicts between the English and the French and the reign of the region moved between them till 1816 after which the French gained authority of Pondicherry until it became the union territory in 1954. The French possessions in India were de facto transferred to the Indian Union and Puducherry became a Union Territory. 280 years of French rule had come to an end. But only in 1963 Puducherry became officially an integral part of India after the French Parliament in Paris ratified the Treaty with India. In the year 1963, the Parliament enacted the Government of Union Territories Act which provides for Legislative Assemblies and Council of Ministers in the Union Territories. In exercise of the powers conferred by Article 239 of the Constitution of India and Section 46 of the Government of Union Territories Act 1963, the President of India has framed the Business of the Government of Puducherry (Allocation)

Rules, 1963. Their presence played a very important role in giving shape to the modern history of Pondicherry and the flourishing commerce, trade, education and infrastructure in the region.

References

1. Directorate of Information Technology, *Pondicherry Municipality*, Pondicherry.
2. National Informatics Centre, *Ministry of Electronics & Information Technology*, Government of India.
3. S. P. SEN, *The French in India (1765–1816)*, Calcutta 1958.
4. K.S. Mathew, ed., *French in India and Indian Nationalism, Vol. II*, Delhi, 1999.
5. Rita Nath Kesari, *The Post Colonial Encounter India: India in the British Imagination*, Pondicherry, 2005.
6. Dr. Sarala Gopalan, *A Situational Analysis Of Women And Girls In Pondicherry*, National Commission For Women New Delhi, 2005.
7. M.P. Sridharan, *Papers on French Colonial Rule in India*, Calicut, 1997.
8. P.A Sampathkumar and Andre Carof mep, *History of Pondicherry Mission: An Outline*, Chennai, 1999.
9. INTACH Pondicherry (2004), *Architectural Heritage of Pondicherry*, 1st ed. Puducherry.
10. Wheeler, R.E.M., Ghosh A., and Deva K., “*Arikamedu: an Indo – Roman Trading Station on the East Coast of India*”, *Ancient India*, vol. 2, 1946.
11. P. Raja & Rita Nath Keshari, *Glimpses of Pondicherry*, Pondicherry, 2005.
12. Soundararajan M., “*Prehistoric, protohistoric and archaeological periods*”, *Gazetteer of India*, Union Territory of Pondicherry, vol. I, 1980.
13. Government of Puducherry (2010), *Brief Analysis Of The Provisional Results Of Census*, 2001.
14. INTACH Pondicherry (2008), *Heritage Conservation in Pondicherry*, 1st ed. Puducherry.
15. Directorate of Information Technology, *Tourism of Puducherry*.
16. INTACH Pondicherry (2010), *INTACH - Pondicherry*.
17. Cyril Antony, *Gazetteer of Pondicherry*, Vol.II, Pondicherry, 1982.